

SUCCINIC ACID DEHYDROGENASE FROM CUCUMBER SEEDS

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The preparation and properties of succinic acid dehydrogenase from cucumber seeds are described. Methylene blue cannot serve as hydrogen acceptor, but the enzyme is a perfect dehydrogenase as it can use a dye of higher $\mu\kappa$ (2:6-dichlorophenolindophenol blue) as hydrogen acceptor. Narcotics inhibit the dehydrogenating property of the enzyme whereas potassium cyanide inhibits the power of utilizing oxygen as hydrogen acceptor. Sodium fluori²a inhibits the dehydrogenating factor considerably and the oxidase factor feebly. Pyrophosphate is inhibitory to both. Incubation for a certain interval with copper sulphate at a concentration, which is usually harmless to the enzyme, greatly inhibits the enzymic activity showing that the enzyme contains a -SH group in the protein molecule.

Succinic dehydrogenase is the most widely studied enzyme. Ever since its discovery by Thunberg (*Zentr. Physiol.*, 1916, 31, 91) from washed muscle it has drawn a good number of workers to this field. The work of Widmark (*Skand. Arch. Physiol.*, 1921, 41, 200), Ohlsson, *ibid.*, 1921, 41, 77), Anderson (*ibid.*, 1928, 52, 187), Alwall (*ibid.*, 1928, 54, 1), Lohmann (*ibid.*, 1930, 58, 45), Sen (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 849), Borsook and Schott (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1931, 82, 535), Ogston and Green (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 1983), and of Potter and Elvehjem (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 117, 341) with the enzyme from animal tissues may be mentioned. Notable also are the experiments of Hopkins, Morgan and LutwakMann (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, 32, 1829) of Euler and Hellström (*British Chemical Abstracts* 1938, A, III, 438, 949; 1939, 623,) and of Bernheim (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1940, 133, 485) on the -SH-group of the enzyme, of Cook and Mapson (*Biochem. J.*, 1930, 24, 1538) and Yudkin (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 1849) on the properties of the enzyme in *B. coli* and of Stotz and Hartings (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 118, 479) on the components of succinate-fumarate systems.

The properties of the enzyme from plant sources have not been studied as yet. The tendency of drawing any conclusion from the study of an enzyme in animal tissues and applying it to that of the plant system is dangerous, as Linderström-Laug (*Ann. Rev. Biochem.* 1937, 6, 48) points out, because of the divergency often met with the same enzyme system from different sources. Thus Reichel and Neff (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1936, 240, 163) reported that neither D. P. N. nor the flavin system is involved in the aerobic activities of citric dehydrogenase from liver while Wagner-Jauregg and Rauen (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1935, 237, 227) found flavoprotein active under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions in the case of the corresponding enzyme from cucumber seeds. The oxidation products were quite different in the two cases and entirely different enzyme systems appear to be involved. A similar divergency is found between the action of α -glycerophosphate dehydrogenase from rabbit muscle (Green, *Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 629) and from cucumber seeds (Wagner-Jauregg and Rauen, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1935, 237, 233).

Cucumber seed has proved to be the source of a host of different dehydrogenases, as is evidenced by the isolation from it of malic dehydrogenase by Thunberg (*Skand. Arch. Physiol.*, 1936, 73, 67) and isocitric, citric and α -glycerophosphate dehydrogenases by Wagner-Jauregg and Rauen (*loc. cit.*). The occurrence of these enzymes led us to think of the possibility that a succinic dehydrogenase which is so widely distributed, may be found in this seed. Consequently, we tried to have an enzyme preparation by mincing cucumber seeds, washing with water to remove the water-soluble enzymes and then extracting with *M/15* secondary sodium phosphate. The enzymic activity of the preparation was tested both anaerobically and aerobically. Using methy-

lene blue as hydrogen acceptor in anaerobic experiments, according to Thunberg's technique, no decolourisation of the dye in presence of succinate ($M/100$) even after 4 to 6 hours was observed. Aerobically a large oxygen uptake ($183/\mu l$ per 30 minutes) was found but in the blank too there was a large oxygen uptake ($140/\mu l$ per 30 minutes). Dialysis of the extract prior to working with it could produce no significant change. Moreover, while in some preparations such oxygen uptake was found, in others there was very little oxygen absorption both in the control and the blank. Such properties as optimum pH , optimum concentration of the substrate, temperature inactivation, action of narcotics and other inhibitors have been studied. Lastly a preliminary experiment was made on the active group of the enzyme on the line of Bernheim (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1940, 133, 485).

The cause of the observation that with some preparations practically no oxygen uptake took place has also been tested. It is found that for active enzyme preparations always fresh cucumber must be used. Preparations from fruits kept for 2—3 days after plucking are completely inactive.

EXPERIMENTAL

In anaerobic experiments a series of Thunberg tubes were prepared each containing 0.5 c.c. of 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol ($1/5000$), 1 c.c. of the enzyme preparation and 0.5 c.c. of succinic acid (neutralised $M/10$ solution). The total volume was made up to 4 c.c. with phosphate buffer ($M/15$) so that the concentration of the substrate stood at $M/80$. The tubes were then evacuated at the room temperature with the help of a Cenco Hyvac pump and the time for complete decolourisation of the dye was noted by placing the tubes in a bath at 38° .

Aerobic experiments were done in Warburg-Barcroft apparatus. One Barcroft vessel contained only the enzyme solution to find out the amount of oxygen absorbed without addition of the substrate. As mentioned before, the amount of oxygen absorbed in the blank was considerable and as such the number of aerobic experiments was limited. It must be mentioned that the oxidising capacity of the enzyme solution varied from sample to sample, and as such no comparison between results of different experiments was possible. Each experiment was, however, carried out with one and the same sample and generally at the same time.

The enzyme solution was prepared by grounding the washed seeds in a mortar with acid washed sand and extracting with $M/15$ secondary sodium phosphate. The extract was then pressed out of the muslin and the solution was used in anaerobic experiments. The whole process was carried out in the cold upon which the success depended.

In aerobic experiments, minced seeds were first washed with water and finally extracted with disodium phosphate as mentioned above. The solution was dialysed in parchment papers for 24 hours against distilled water and the dialysed clear solution was used. The results are given in Table I.

Inactivation by Heat.—3 C.c. of the enzyme solution were placed in a series of test tubes and kept immersed for 10 minutes in baths at different temperatures. The solution was then brought down to 30° and the dehydrogenase activity was measured anaerobically, as before. The results are given in Table III.

It will be seen from Table III that the activity of the enzyme remains intact even after heating to 40° . After that, there is a gradual decrease in activity, and at 60° the enzyme is completely inactivated, its reduction time being beyond that of the blank. Another point should also be noted. In separating fumarase from succinic acid dehydrogenase of animal tissues the usual procedure is to heat the enzyme solution to 50° , when fumarase is inactivated and the

succinic acid dehydrogenase activity remains behind. A similar procedure adopted in the case of the plant enzyme, however, would be detrimental as along with the inactivation of the fumarase the cucumber succino-dehydrogenase will also lose about 50% of its activity. In the experiments described, therefore, no such separation was attempted.

TABLE I

Variation of activity
with p_{H}
Temp. = 38°

p_{H} of the Reduction Activity
medium. time (T) (100 = 1/T)

TABLE III

Heat inactivation of
the enzyme.

Temp. Reduction Activity
of in- time (T). (100/T).
cubation.

TABLE IV

Action of narcotics on the
dehydrogenase
Temp. = 38°

Narcotic used. Reduction time (A). Reduction time of the control (B). Percentage inhibition $\frac{100(1/B - 1/A)}{1/B}$

6.4	16	6.3	30°	13 mins	7.7	Vanillin (0.1%)	20½ mins.	18 mins.	12.2
6.6	16	6.3	35°	13	7.7	Urethane (1%)	23	"	21.7
6.8	14	7.1	40°	13	7.7	Barbitone (1%)	21½	"	17.2
7.2	11	9.1	45°	16	6.3	Octyl alcohol (0.001%)	24	"	25.0
7.4	15	6.7	50°	23	4.3				
7.7	22	4.5	55°	40	2.5				
8.0	32	3.1	60°	44	Nil				

In Table III time of decolourisation in the blank = 44 minutes.

In Table I the time of decolourisation of the blank was from 45 minutes to 1 hour and in some cases more. The optimum p_{H} is thus 7.2, a value very near to that found with the dehydrogenase of animal tissues, the optimum p_{H} of the latter being 7.4.

Optimum Substrate Concentration

Table II shows the effect of substrate concentration on the activity of the enzyme.

TABLE II

Temp. = 38°

Tubes.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Enzyme (c.c.)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Dye (c.c.) 1/5000	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Phos. buffer (c.c.) M/15	1.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	1.5	2.0
Final conc. of succinic acid	M/40	M/80	M/160	M/320	M/640	M/1280
Reduction time (T)	9.0	9.0	10.0	11.7	18.2	25.0
Activity (100/T)	11.1	11.1	10.0	8.6	5.5	4.0

Action of Narcotics.—Sea (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 849) studied the action of a large number of narcotics such as vanillin, phenylurea, diethylurea, valeroneitrile, propionitrile, ethylurethane and phenylurethane on succinodehydrogenase of the animal tissues. Because of the war most of the narcotics were not available. The concentration of the narcotics was so arranged that the activity fell from 10 to 30%. The results are given in Table IV.

In each of the tube were placed 2 c.c. of the enzyme, 0.5 c.c. of the substrate, 0.5 c.c. dye solution and 0.5 c.c. of the narcotic under question at the required concentration. The total volume was made to 4 c.c. by adding phosphate buffer of p_n 7.2. The same enzyme solution was used throughout so that a comparison of the action of different narcotics was possible.

Action of other Inhibitors.—Stotz and Hastings (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 118, 479) measured the inhibition of the succinic acid dehydrogenase produced by a number of different substances such as arsenite, arsenate, selenite, fluoride and potassium cyanide. They found that sodium selenite and potassium cyanide stopped respectively the dehydrogenating and oxidising function completely without affecting the other at all. Fluoride affected both the factors while pyrophosphate affected only the oxidase. Potter and Elvehjem (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 117, 341) also studied the action of those substances upon this enzyme prepared from a homogeneous suspension of the chick kidney. They found almost similar results with arsenite, arsenate, selenite, and potassium cyanide. With fluoride, however, the inhibition was found to be practically nil. It seemed, therefore, of interest to see how these substances behaved with the plant enzyme. It was found that sodium pyrophosphate and fluoride affected both the aerobic and anaerobic activity while sodium arsenite and potassium cyanide affected only the oxidase factor. The results are shown in Tables V and VI.

TABLE V
Action of inhibitors on
anaerobic activity

Temp. = 38°

Inhibitor.	Conc.	Reduction time (A).	Reduction time of control (B).	% inhibition $\frac{100(B-A)}{A}$
Sodium pyrophosphate.	M/100	34	16.5	48.4
	M/300	26	16.5	36.5
	M/1000	19	16.5	13.2
Sodium fluoride	M/100	22.5	17	24.4
	M/300	20	17	15
Sodium arsenite	M/100	18.2	18	Nil.
Potassium cyanide.	M/100	19	19	Nil.

TABLE VI
Effect of inhibitors on
aerobic activity

Temp. = 38°

Oxygen uptake in μ l per 2 c.c. enzyme soln. per hr.

Inhibitor.	Conc. of the inhibitor.				Enzyme in c.c.	Treatment of the enzyme.	CuSO ₄ in c.c. 10 ⁻⁴ M.	Phos. buffer (c.c.)	Water in c.c.	Substrate M/20 in c.c.	Oxygen per hour. (μ l)
	Control.	M/100.	M/300.	M/1000.							
Sodium arsenite	430	159	216	344	2	—	—	2	2	1	388
Sodium arsenate	395	301	329	398	2	Not incubated previously	2	2	—	1	380
Sodium fluoride	412	382	400	426	2	Incubated for one hour	2	2	—	1	0
Pot. cyanide	420	6	43	134	2	—	—	2	2	1	370
	412	251	310	380	2	Not incubated previously	0.5	2	1.5	1	369
Sodium pyro-phosphate.	412	251	310	380	2	Not incubated previously	0.5	2	1.5	1	369
	412	251	310	380	2	Incubated for one hour	0.5	2	1.5	1	58

It will be seen from Table VI that potassium cyanide produces near about 100% inhibition at a concentration of 0.01 M. The action of arsenite upon the aerobic activity is also con-

siderable being about 63% at a concentration of 0.01 *M*. In contrast to the action of arsenite, that of arsenate is considerably small.

On the -SH group of the Enzyme.

Hopkins and Morgan (*Biochem. J.*, 1938, 32, 611) showed that when washed and minced tissues are incubated anaerobically for adequate periods with solutions of glutathione (GSSG) at pH 7.4, the succinic acid dehydrogenase is completely inactivated. On the other hand the original activity of the enzyme is fully regained when the preparations, so treated, are subsequently re-incubated with the reduced form of glutathione (GSH). Hopkins *et al* (*Biochem. J.*, 1938, 32, 1829) also studied the influence of other substances known or supposed to inhibit the enzyme by combining or reacting with the -SH group and also the influence of other substances in protecting the enzyme from such inactivation. The enzyme is inactivated by copper, maleic acid and iodoacetic acid, substances that react with the -SH group while malonic, succinic and fumaric acids protect the enzyme from inactivation by GSSG. Bernheim (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1940, 133, 485) studied the action of copper on the enzyme. The inhibitory action of copper on succinic acid dehydrogenase is the result of its catalytic effect on the oxidation of -SH group of the enzyme protein. It follows, therefore, that a concentration of copper which causes no inhibition immediately after its addition to the enzyme, should cause an inhibition if incubated for sufficient time before its activity is tested. On this principle, the action of copper sulphate on the plant enzyme was determined. Anaerobically the experiment could not be done since in presence of phosphate buffer, copper sulphate solution gives a precipitate of copper phosphate. Further, the addition 2 : 6-dichlorophenol-indophenol to it produces a pink colour which persists indefinitely. The same pink colour was obtained even without addition of the buffer. Aerobic experiments were, therefore, resorted to.

It was found that immediate addition of 2 c.c. of 10^{-4} *M* copper sulphate solution to a mixture of 2 c.c. of enzyme, 1 c.c. of substrate and 2 c.c. buffer (to make a total volume of 7 c.c.) produced from 2 to 3% inhibition of the enzyme. (There was a slight oxidation of the copper sulphate in presence of the enzyme, probably due to its passage to a higher state of oxidation, which was carefully accounted for). Another 2 c.c. portion of the enzyme were first incubated for about an hour with the same volume of copper sulphate solution at the same concentration, and after the required time, phosphate buffer (2 c.c.) and substrate (1 c.c.) were added and the activity was measured. There was no oxygen uptake indicating complete inactivation of the enzyme. Copper sulphate solution at a low concentration (0.5 c.c. of 10^{-4} *M* solution in a total volume of 7 c.c.) was also used in a second series of experiments. The result was similar but this time initial inactivation was practically nil whereas inactivation after one hour's incubation was about 70%. The result, represented in Table VII, is interesting and shows that the plant enzyme probably also contains the -SH group.